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“FILIPINOS IN WILDERNESS”

My Dad and I were at the Safari watching the different species of animals. We have seen ferocious tigers, giant elephants, striking colors of zebras, pool of crocodiles, and the regal lion known as the King of the Jungle. As we started our Safari ride, we are welcomed by the group of elephants. We are amazed of how the giant elephants display their behavior by snapping their trunks in front us, letting the children touch and feed them and leaning on each other. The zebras on the other hand are unique in their own ways with their exclusive stripes, we enjoyed watching them confronting the predators and sometimes successfully defending themselves with their powerful kicks. After watching the zebras and the elephants, we went to the habitat of the tigers, they were in grassland and we saw them mimic their natural environment. As we watch the tigers, one particular tiger caught my attention, he is facing me squarely and I have seen how big his pupils are. It seems that his goal is to intimidate us maybe to emphasize his territorial attitude because we are not part of their habitat. While I was watching the tiger, our tour guide told us that tigers have excellent vision enabling them to see clearly during daylight due to large pupils and lenses. They can also see six times clearly than humans at night that makes them efficient hunters. I saw the other tiger stalking a goat and I was amazed how he rapidly chased the goat and enjoyed eating its carcass. Few minutes after, that tiger is holding my gaze. As I watched him closely, I saw his muscular body and powerful legs. I told my dad, “He must be the King of the Jungle”. But our tour guide rebutted by saying that he is not the King of the jungle. I retorted, “Then who is the king of the jungle?” he replied, “We have other animals to see in our Safari ride.”

We then went on to another habitat and there we saw giant Asian Black Bears, they are heavy-set animals with distinguishing coloration, we watched them eating meat and plants. They are very adorable just like a big stuff toy. But similar to other animals in the wild, our tour guide told us, “They can be dangerous, you might end up inside their tummy if you pet them”. Looking at them closely, I saw that bears are solitary animals, “Unlike tigers, they are not territorial” said the tour guide “they might tolerate other bears and certain animals within their home range” the tour guide added.

Then we went on to another habitat. On our way we saw a fire. We felt scared however, we realized that it is part of the habitat they termed as savanna. It is where the majestic lions shelter. In the excitement of one of the passengers, he blurted, “Look! The King of the Jungle!” My dad and I became thrilled and the rest of the passengers were amazed. We were all thrilled to finally see a pride of lions in the wild because we only watch them on animal documentaries. Moreover, we watched carefully the lions and how they react to us and to the rest of their pride. What captivates me is to see the body structure of a lion. His mane is a prominent feature distinguishing him from the rest of the animals in the wild. Although lions and tigers are being compared both as strong and dominant animals however, tigers are solitary animals and territorial on its own.

Unlike tigers, I have seen that lions are sociable animals and they live with their groups consisting of related females, cubs and few dominant males. I still wonder why the lion is dubbed as the King of the Jungle? What attitude that lions exude that qualify them as the King of the Jungle? As I look closely, they have a strong connection with their pride and work together to hunt and protect their territory altogether...

A few moments have passed and we were suddenly petrified when we saw a scene of lion and tiger having a close fight. We have just watched a scene of a brutal display of power and predatory skill. The thick mane of a lion protects his neck from the attack. His thick mane is an opportunity for him to have a powerful bite without putting himself in dangerous situation. While the tiger has an agile and flexible character, he used his sharp claws targeting the vulnerable part of his opponent. During the close fight, we saw that tigers' attacks use strategies of evasive maneuvers. The tiger's strong muscular built attacked the lion with its paw causing the lion to bleed and the lion roared. We were terrified by how blaring the lion's roar. "It seems that the lion was about to die!" dad exclaimed. The tiger's attack when he pounces, is strong enough to break bones and kill his opponent. Everyone in the Safari was entertained with this kind of unusual show. It is like watching gladiators fight in an arena and we were the spectators.

Several moments have passed and everybody was all eyes to the big cats waiting who will survive. Unexpectedly, the tiger exited the fight and vanished from the savanna. Both cats were all bleeding to death however the lion stood firm in the fight and never left his habitat. My dad suddenly blurted, "well that made the Lion as the King of the Jungle because in hard situation, he never leaves. He is a good leader of his pride". I realized that he is right because the lion fought to the bitter end and remained firm and unyielding to the tiger's attack. I have observed too that in that scene the tiger was the intruder because savanna is not the habitat of the tigers. Maybe the tiger is just proving himself in another's territory.

All of us enjoyed the Safari ride, we thought that the tour is about to end, however, "there is more" said the tour guide. We then proceeded to another habitat. This time it is an aquatic habitat. There we passed by mangroves and rivers. The stillness of the river is very relaxing however, like a bolt from the blue, we have seen a huge reptile moving on the river. One of the passengers shouted, "It's a crocodile!" When I saw the reptile, it's indeed huge enough that it seemed he ate all the prey he saw in his habitat for I never seen a crocodile that huge. I was thinking that he might be the only living crocodile in his habitat and he must have already eaten all the other members of his community of reptiles. Nevertheless, we have seen 3 smaller crocodiles swimming on the river and in a few moments, we have seen other crocodiles floating until we realized that the river we are passing by is a crocodile infested river.

Unlike the other predators, these creatures look nasty and sickening for their bodies seem to be a combination of different nasty aquatic animals. Their bodies come in shades of brown or gray and others we saw were in greenish or reddish tints. On the side of the river, we saw other crocodiles sun bathing on the riverbanks, as if they were having their vacation on a private beach. Our tour guide said, "crocodiles usually stay on the riverbanks to sun bathe in order to regulate their body temperature. In that river bank, a kangaroo suddenly appeared looking for water to drink. The crocodiles in the riverbank did not move pretending as tired and sleeping as always. The kangaroo must have left its troop and while he is exploring, he must have trailed into another habitat. When the kangaroo is about to approach the river to drink, he was swiftly caught by the crocodile hiding on the river. A sumptuous early afternoon snack for the crocodiles and those crocodiles in sun bathing went to the carcass to join their fellow crocodile that caught the kangaroo. To our surprise, one of the crocodiles in the sun bathe grabbed the bigger part of the carcass from the other crocodiles and ate it immediately leaving its tummy to bulge enormously. And then it went again to its previous

post waiting for another opportunity to grab. In the innocence of the kangaroo, it became the victim of cunning tricks of the pretentious crocodiles.

The other crocodiles saw the left-over from the carcass of the kangaroo and they gathered altogether to feast. "Tamad siguro yung isa, o baka siya ang leader dahil siya ang kumain ng malaking part ng kangaroo" one of the Filipino passengers exclaimed. The tour guide understood what the passenger said and replied, "Crocodiles are misconstrued as lazy predators but in reality, they conserve their energy for their future hunt. That is why we find them resting most of the time." The tour guide added, "The resting behavior of crocodiles is a key part of their ambush predator lifestyle." Another Filipino passenger exclaimed, "hindi pala tamad, kundi oportunista..." I realized that my dad and I were not the only Filipinos on that trail. To my surprise, we were all Filipinos in that Safari at the very center of the wilderness.

Those facts from these various animals we have encountered along our journey reminded me of the nature of humans we encountered in the social fabric of humanity. We left the habitats of predators with a feeling of wonder, awe and astonishment of Allah's creations. I realized that animals' habitat is no different from the habitat of humans. As humans we encounter different types of people along the way. Just like these species, reality shows that people possess the dominant and less dominant human character. Some are the perpetrators, and others are the victim. In the mainstream, it is always the lower class who plays the role of a victim and those who possess power and money control the course of the human habitat. Just like the goat and the kangaroo, they are likened to a bait in the game. Because of their weak and innocent character, it made them as the subject of oppression, persecution and tyranny. However, it takes courage to play the role of a lion that is strong, unyielding and firm from the invaders. Nevertheless, just like the tiger, your opponent will only be threatened when he sees you battling the maneuverings and manipulations.

In reality, you can only earn an amount of respect by how you let others perceive you. One must possess self-reliance, independence, vigilance and foresight to be able to survive. It is the only way that intruders will know their place when they see you firm and know where you stand in difficult situation.

The safari experience is awesome. We left the park and rode a taxi, a scenic view of the Sentosa is relaxing in the eyes and while I was looking at the flowers along the road of Singapore, I was reminded of the animals I have seen in our Safari journey. It reminded me of how those animals control their habitat, their territory. Their character traits in the wild highly influence the course of their lives.

I was thinking before that being influential is not necessary. But it hits me to realize, just like these animals, we Filipinos are in the wilderness. We are victims of the rotten system and the selfish maneuverings of our society's system. The strong eats the weak and the strong remains powerful. At times someone has a need to maintain power to resist others' domination. It is important to reflect on the traits of the lion, that is strong, independent and protective of its own territory. Being good and kind is not enough in this cruel world but to be strong and self-reliant with a solid foresight and vigilance is indispensable for we are surrounded by perpetrators and predators in the human wilderness. Self-reliance, gives somebody the power and the freedom to decide his course of action without letting others decide for him or even dictate where he should be.

In our daily grind, everyone can be a victim of manipulations unless he has the power to resist. However, one can only execute resistance if one possesses influence, self-reliance and determination. Our society is in the

wilderness and it has always been a power struggle and contestation of authority. The strong and powerful have the pool of options to control how the society operates.

We arrived at the restaurant and I saw a colorful ice cream buffet. My dad asked me, “you choose”.

